

NEWSERA - Citizen Science as the
new paradigm for Science
Communication

Deliverable 6.4

NEWSERA project

official video

Revision: v1.0

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DELIVERABLE DETAILS

Due date: December 31th, 2020

Actual submission date: January 11, 2021

Project start date: January 1st, 2020

Duration: 36 months

Work Package concerned: WP6

Concerned work package leader: Lisa Lazzarato

Dissemination level:

- PU:** Public (must be available on the website)
- CO:** Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
- Cl:** Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

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Revision history:

revision	date	Contributor	Description
v1.0	08.01.2020	Rosa Arias, Oriol Agulló (Science for Change)	Final Draft

STATEMENT OF ORIGINALITY

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise.

Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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1. Acronyms

Acronym	Description
CitSciComm	Citizen Science Communication
FB	formicablu
FC.ID	FCIENCIAS.ID Associação para a Investigação e Desenvolvimento de Ciências
FECYT	Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology
IBERCIVIS	Fundación Ibercivis
SfC	Science for Change
UNIPD	Università degli Studi di Padova
WP	Work Package

2. Introduction

This Deliverable describes the NEWSERA project official video, as defined in Task 6.3 (“Cross media production”) of Work Package 6 “Dissemination and communication actions”.

The NEWSERA video is aimed at presenting the project to the general public. It is developed according to the project visual identity (illustrated in D6.3 NEWSERA Visual identity). It uses some of the partners' voices and animated graphics to explain the project and its core activities.

COVID-19 restrictions changed the video's original idea: to use the shooting of at least two co-creation labs (CitSciComm Labs). Since labs were postponed, decentralised to the three project countries (Spain, Italy and Portugal) and switched to online meetings, only shooting taken in Barcelona in February 2020, at the Kick off meeting of the project, was used.

3. Script

The video production was based on a concept, converted into a script and discussed and approved by all the consortium members. The script presented the visual content (shooting or graphic animation) and the corresponding audio (partners voices or voice-over), as shown in the following table.

Visual	Audio
Animated intro, with Newsera logo and payoff	
Cristina Luis (FC.ID)	“Newsera is a project that wishes to bring citizen science into the field of science communication.”
Federico Neresini (UNIPD)	“Newsera is a great challenge, trying to match the best of the citizen science and the best of the science communication.”
Izaskun Lacunza (FECYT)	“We really want to explore how citizen science can contribute to science, to be an essential part of the policy making.”
Ana Elorza (FECYT)	“Making citizens aware and connected to their reality and part of their reality.”
Animation + Voice-over	In citizen science projects, the public is part of the scientific research. Science becomes more democratic, accessible and easier to understand. NEWSERA studies how citizen science can become a powerful tool for science communication.
Maite Pelacho (IBERCIVIS)	“Communication is an essential part of participation.”
Francisco Sanz (IBERCIVIS)	“Now the science is top to down, and the communication is going top to down, but using citizen science as a tool for communication [means] that now citizens can have a main role in the communication of science.”
Animation + Voice-over	The core of NEWSERA are the #CitSciComm Labs , or Citizen Science Communication Labs: in these co-creation events, citizen science practitioners work with members of the general public, academic scientists, entrepreneurs, policy makers and journalists. Together, they create innovative communication strategies that can reach different stakeholders better. The results of the CitSciComm Labs will be used to create five Communication Blueprints , that explain how to create an effective communication strategy for your citizen science project depending on your target. The Blueprints will be public and accessible to everyone.
Rosa Arias (SfC)	“Newsera is super ambitious, so we want to talk to many many different stakeholders. We are in citizen science so we need to talk to everybody, like

	citizens, politicians, industry, and also other scientists. We also need to talk with data journalists and science communicators.”
Elisabetta Tola (FB)	“Data journalism and citizen science can be significantly of mutual benefit. Data journalists need data to work on their investigation, to build their stories and citizen science projects can be a very valuable source of original data. When the data are not of interest for the media, sometimes citizen science project are focused on very specialized type of investigation, the citizen science projects can still use data journalism to empower their communication, to use the tool and the approaches used in journalism to make a better case for their project.
Izaskun Lacunza (FECYT)	“I think that this project will be very important, because we are going to put together stakeholders that are not usually together, such as citizens, researchers and policy makers.”
Coverage footage of co-creation session at Kick off meeting	NEWSERA will integrate citizen science and science communication, to show that citizen science initiatives can become a bridge that connects scientists, government, industry and the local communities.
Animation + voice-over	NEWSERA is...
Paolo Giardullo (UNIPD)	“innovation”
Maite Pelacho (IBERCIVIS)	“trust”
Oriol Agullo (SfC)	“open science”
Rosa Arias (SfC)	“motivation and knowledge”
Francisco Sanz (IBERCIVIS)	“data and participation”
Izaskun Lacunza (FECYT)	“democracy”
Cristina Luis (FC.ID)	“citizen, science, and communication.”
Credits	

Table 1. Script of the NEWSERA project video

Figure 1. Screenshots of the NEWSERA video.

4. Dissemination

The NEWSERA video is uploaded on a dedicated YouTube channel (https://youtu.be/gXe_hle_K8k) and embedded on the project website's homepage (<https://newsera2020.eu>). This choice will simply give access to metrics (views,

sharing, etc.), provided by the YouTube platform. It will allow to easily add subtitles in different languages (at least English, Spanish, Portuguese and Italian).

The video will be shared through Twitter and other social media used by NEWSERA partners. It is also intended to be a communication tool to introduce the project at events briefly and thus be regularly used.